

THE USAGE OF DIFFERENT STYLISTIC DEVICES IN "A ROSE FOR EMILY" BY WILLIAM FAULKNER

Usmonova Zarina Habibovna

Senior teacher of English Linguistics Department

Sattorova Shakhrizoda Umedjon qizi

1st year student of Master degree

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Abstract

Using literal language in a unique way shows the great ability of author in creating masterpieces. This paper highlights a stylistic analysis of "A Rose for Emily", a short story by William Faulkner which is a bright example of literalism. The work consists some information about the author and his work, then the description of stylistic devices and analysis of various types of them. This analysis is done by adopting outstanding researchers' approaches to analyze the author's work and stylistic devices. Moreover, the function of them and their importance of increasing the artistic value of the work is also mentioned.

Key words: style, stylistics, metaphor, metonymy, literalism, graphon, onomatopoeia.

Introduction

William Faulkner's "A Rose for Emily" was first published in Forum on April 30, 1930, and was the first of Faulkner's short stories to appear in a national publication. "A Rose for Emily" is set in the fictional town of Jefferson, Mississippi, which is based on Oxford, Mississippi, the author's hometown. Faulkner chooses an unusual narrator for "A Rose for Emily" in the form of the collective voice of the townspeople who witness the events of Emily Grierson's life and speculate on the rumors that surround her. It is the story of a woman isolated from her community and takes drastic and horrifying measures to rid herself of loneliness. William Faulkner says the rose in the title is meant as a gesture of respect to Emily, in the sense that people might present a rose or a flower to someone they like. People who are isolated and lonely will sometimes do anything to combat the loneliness. In "A Rose for Emily", Emily lives alone without affection from anyone. She is so desperate to end her loneliness that she kills a man and keeps his body in a locked room in her home. When the onlookers see the indentation in the pillow beside Homer's decayed body, they know that someone has been lying beside the corpse. When they discover the single strand of "iron-grey hair", they realize that Emily has been sleeping with the corpse for many years. A woman of high social status is isolated from the

rest of the townspeople in Jefferson, Mississippi because they believe she think she is too good for them. Emily meets a Yankee laborer named Homer Barron, who suires her around town. She wants to marry him, but he likely refuses. To prevent him from leaving, she poisons him. After her death, the townspeople are shocked to learn that she has kept his corpse in her house, and she has been lying beside his decayed body for years. Homer Barron is probably not married to Emily. He does escort her around town, and she buys gifts for him when she plans to marry him. But when he attempts to leave her, she poisons him. Emily is so lonely that she cannot allow him to leave. In addition, she would have to face the embarrassment of knowing that Homer has jilted her. Since Emily has already been the topic of discussion, she would likely want to avoid providing additional ammunition for gossip. Emily remains distant from us as readers, and we never learn about her inner life: we only ever see her from the outside, through the eyes of the townspeople. The work "A rose for Emily" is a decent story which blends first and third-person narration, realism, past memories and present events.

"A subfield of applied linguistics known as stylistics studies and interprets spoken language and/or texts of all kinds in terms of their linguistic and tonal style. Style is the unique range of language that is employed by various people and/or in various contexts. The study and interpretation of written and spoken language with respect to its linguistic and tonal style is known as stylistics, a subfield of applied linguistics. Style is the unique mix of language that is employed by various people, groups, and/or contexts. The primary characteristic that defines a stylistic device (SD) is the binary opposition of two meanings of the used unit, one of which emerges within a specific context and is contextual, and the other of which is normatively set in the language. The poetic function was one of six general functions of language he described in the lecture"

Michael Halliday is an important figure in the development of British stylistics . M.A.K. Halliday defined linguistic stylistics as "the description of literary texts, by methods derived from general linguistic theory, using the categories of the description of the language as a whole; and the comparison. of each text with others, by the same and by different authors".

Stylistics, a branch of applied linguistics, is the study and interpretation of texts of all types and/or spoken language in regard to their linguistic and tonal style, where style is the particular variety of language used by different individuals and/or in different situations or settings. For example, the vernacular, or everyday language may be used among casual friends, whereas

more formal language, with respect to grammar, pronunciation or accent, and lexicon or choice of words, is often used in a cover letter and résumé and while speaking during a job interview” . Stylistics is closely related to the theory of the creation of a text, a theory which I believe is capable of giving wiser considerations to the creative writing process .

I.R. Galperin classified stylistic devices as following:

1. Lexical stylistic devices are stylistic devices that rely on the binary opposition of lexical meanings, independent of the utterance's syntactical organization.

2. Syntactical stylistic devices, which are stylistic devices based on the binary opposition of syntactical meanings of different semantic interpretations.

3. Lexico-syntactical stylistic devices, which are based on the binary opposition of lexical meanings combined with a defined syntactical arrangement of the lexical units used.

In this work we can encounter several stylistic devices such as metaphor, symbolism, simile, imagery, rhyme, onomatopoeia, graphon, pause and so on, which serve to express emotiveness and the situation of that time. The enigmatic existence of Miss Emily Grierson is the subject of this brief gothic tale. It symbolizes the various challenges that the main character faces and shows how societal change affects people on a personal level. For example,

“...a small, fat woman in black, with a thin gold chain descending to her waist and vanishing into her belt, leaning on an ebony cane with a tarnished gold head. Her skeleton was small and spare; perhaps that was why what would have been merely plumpness in another was obesity in her.” In this paragraph we can see the description of a woman who is the main character with different kinds of descriptive words and phrases which illustrate the process of imagery. Imagery a literary strategy used in poetry, novels, and other works of writing to evoke a mental image or idea in the reader through vivid description. Language's use of imagery attempts to convey the text's sensory and emotional content in addition to painting a picture.

“...they could hear the invisible watch ticking at the end of the gold chain.” The word ticking is showing the features of a stylistic device which is called onomatopoeia. It is using words that sound like the noise they make. This can give a poem or other piece of literature an intriguing and dramatic effect as well.

“...dammit, sir,” Judge Stevens said, “will you accuse a lady to her face of smelling bad?...” in this excerpt the word “dammit” is a bright example for graphon. Prose only uses graphon to denote hazy, unintelligible, or careless

pronunciation (temporary factors: immaturity, inebriation, lack of knowledge about the subject matter; permanent factors: social status, educational background, territorial status; distinct articulation: whispering, stammering etc.

There are lots of examples that relate to punctuation. For instance, "I have no taxes in Jefferson. Tobe!" The Negro appeared. "Show these gentlemen out." The exclamation mark after the word Tobe indicates that it is an imperative form which is told in a strict tone.

A metaphor is a form of speech in which two unlike things are compared. Metaphor is a literary device that, without explicitly using the terms "like" or "as," establishes implicit analogies. Declaring two objects to be identical in comparison, as opposed to merely similar, is done through the use of metaphor. This is helpful when expressing abstract facts in literature by using certain imagery or ideas. In "A rose for Emily" metaphor can be seen anywhere. For example, "... gasoline pumps..." the drops of gasoline around miss Emily's house is used as gasoline pumps. This is the author's unique way of using metaphor.

"...her eyes, lost in the fatty ridges of her face, looked like two small pieces of coal pressed into a lump of dough as they moved from one face to another..."

In this example, the ridges of her face is resembled like coal pressed into a lump of dough which means the black spots or edges of her face look like two pieces of coal on a dough. By describing this the author is using a slight imagery to make the readers understand the level of his stylistic knowledge.

Conclusion

A Rose for Emily's stylistic analysis helps the reader effectively comprehend the meaning of the book's characters, themes, structure, etc. The stylistic devices that are used in this masterpiece enhance the value of the work and show the author's ability to describe people, things and events in a professional way. It is important to emphasize that the model and analysis lead to a deeper comprehension of the text's narrative elements. It is anticipated that the analysis will help with the other tales' study.

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